

The importance of cross-reactive memory T cells against coronaviruses in the design of second generation of COVID-19 vaccines

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Recently Kundu and coworkers published a study in which they assessed 52 COVID-19 household contacts to capture immune responses at the earliest timepoints after SARS-CoV-2 exposure. Using a dual cytokine FLISpot assay on peripheral blood mononuclear cells, researchers enumerated the frequency of T cells specific for spike, nucleocapsid, membrane, envelope and ORF1 SARS-CoV-2 epitopes that cross-react with human endemic coronaviruses. Researchers observed higher frequencies of cross-reactive ($p=0.0139$), and nucleocapsid-specific ($p=0.0355$) IL-2 secreting memory T cells in contacts who remained PCR-negative despite exposure ($n=26$), when compared with those who convert to PCR-positive ($n=26$), whilst no significant difference in the frequency of responses to spike is observed, hinting at a limited protective function of spike-cross-reactive T cells. Authors concluded that these results are consistent with pre-existing non-spike cross-reactive memory T cells protecting SARS-CoV-2 naive contacts from infection, thereby supporting the inclusion of non-spike antigens, especially ORF1 and N (nucleocapsid) antigens, in second-generation vaccines against COVID-19 (1).

Taking into account the limited protective function of spike-cross-reactive T cells and more effective protective function of N- and ORF-1-cross-reactive T cells as demonstrated in the above mentioned study, the toxicity of the spike (S) protein (2-5), serious adverse effects reported for Wuhan spike protein-based up-to-date available vaccines (6), the increasing epidemiological relevance of the COVID-19 vaccinated population (7), and the emergence of new, increasingly vaccine-resistant strains with significant number of

mutations in the S protein, such as Omicron with 32 mutations in S protein (8, 9) and IHU with 46 mutations in S protein (10), there is a need for the development of new generation of COVID-19 vaccines, based on non-spike antigens, preferably ORF1 and N antigens, that would be theoretically less toxic, associated with less serious adverse effects, and more effective against emerging new strains, which would be attributable to the cross reactive ORF-1 and N specific T-cells, but more research is mandatory.

CONCLUSION

The importance of vaccination can be observed on the individual level, meaning the reduction of the risk for severe COVID-19, and on the population level, meaning the reduction of the transmission of the virus, repression of the virus and induction of loss-of-function mutations in the SARS-CoV-2. Non-spike antigens based multi-epitope vaccine could be a promising option for the new generation of COVID-19 vaccines.

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